

Effect of herbicides on weed control in transplanted rice, Kota, India.

Treatment ^a	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at harvest		Cost-to-benefit ratio ^b
		1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	
		2,4-D EE (G)	0.8	6.7	5.2	312	281	2.8	2.9	
2,4D EE (G)	1.0	6.9	5.6	321	283	2.7	2.9	167	71	12.5
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.1	6.1	5.8	311	290	3.2	2.8	190	85	–
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.15	6.3	5.8	324	295	3.4	2.9	149	82	–
Thiobencarb (G)	1.0	6.7	5.8	320	297	2.9	3.0	188	78	14.5
Thiobencarb (G)	1.5	6.7	5.9	295	284	3.0	2.8	185	70	9.9
Anilofos (EC)	0.3	6.5	4.8	298	295	2.9	2.7	209	95	–
Anilofos (EC)	0.4	6.2	5.3	310	271	2.9	2.8	189	89	–
Butachlor (G)	1.0	6.6	5.4	290	242	3.0	3.0	192	95	12.4
Butachlor (G)	1.5	6.8	5.7	315	253	2.9	2.9	190	96	9.5
Pendimethalin (G)	1.0	7.1	6.1	332	267	3.5	3.3	130	69	18.4
Pendimethalin (G)	1.5	6.9	5.7	310	267	2.8	3.0	163	75	10.7
Butachlor (EN)	1.0	5.7	5.6	299	261	2.5	2.8	210	100	10.8
Butachlor (EN)	1.5	6.1	5.7	300	252	3.3	2.8	180	104	8.5
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	–	7.0	6.0	323	262	3.5	3.5	134	15	7.0
Unweeded check	–	4.6	4.0	264	236	2.4	2.3	232	166	–
CD (0.05)		0.2	0.2	3	4	0.1	0.3	2	2	–

^a EE = ethyl ester, G = granules, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, EN = emulsion. Cost of 2,4-D 4G, \$1/kg; thiobencarb 10 G, \$2.15/kg; butachlor 5G, \$1.1/kg; pendimethalin S G, \$1/kg; butachlor 50 EN, \$10/liter; oxyfluorfen and anilofos, not available. ^b Grain, \$160/t; C:B averaged over 2 yr.

Pendimethalin at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, thiobencarb at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, and 2,4-D at 1.0 kg ai/ha were effective in controlling weeds (see table). These treatments had significantly higher grain yield, more effective tillers, and higher panicle weight than the unweeded check. The highest benefit-to-cost ratio was with pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Yield loss to rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*

E. I. Jonathan and B. Vela-putham, Nematology Laboratory, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Trichy 5, India

We conducted two experiments with potted plants to determine yield loss to *H. oryzae*.

IR20 seedlings raised in sterile soil were transplanted 21 d after sowing at 4 seedlings/pot. Treatments were rice root nematodes inoculated at 1 and at 10/g soil and an untreated check, in 8

Effect of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* on height and yield of rice. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85.

Treatment (nematodes/g soil)	Plant ht (cm)			Grain		Straw	
	30 DT	60 DT	At harvest	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)
0	38 a	62 a	79 a	44.1 a	–	34.1 a	–
1	34 b	58 b	70 b	32.2 b	26.9	26.0 b	22.9
10	30 c	54 c	68 c	26.6 c	39.7	19.7 c	42.2
CD (0.05)		1		5.2	–	3.5	–

^a Mean for 2 pot experiments, with 8 replications each. DT = days after transplanting. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

replications.

Yield losses were 27% with 1 nematode/g soil and 40% with 10

nematodes/g soil (see table). Straw yields were 23% less with 1 nematode and 42% less with 10 nematodes. □

Control of rice root nematode with carbofuran

B.N. Routaray, H. Sahoo, and S. N. Das, Nematology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

The effect of carbofuran on populations of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella*

mucronata and on growth characteristics of rice were measured in microplot field experiments in 1983 and 1984 rainy seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 4 treatments and 5 replications in 16-m² subplots.

Treatments were seedlings from an untreated nursery (T1), seedlings from a

carbofuran-treated nursery (T2), seedlings from the untreated nursery with carbofuran applied 50 d after transplanting (DT) (T3), and seedlings from the carbofuran-treated nursery with carbofuran at 50 DT (T4). All applications were at 1 kg ai/ha.

Experimental field soil was loamy clay with pH 6.4. Recommended NPK

fertilizer was applied. Healthy 30-d-old Jaya seedlings were transplanted at 20×15-cm spacing. Other cultural practices were as needed.

Preplanting nematode populations per 200 cc soil did not differ significantly by year but varied within years: 122.4-134.6 in 1983 and 109.6-126.0 in 1984.

At harvest, *H. mucronata* numbers were very low in soil samples of treated nursery and treated plot (see table). Nematode populations per gram root also were low. The number of flowering tillers was higher and fresh root weight was greater. Yields increased with increasing carbofuran application. □

Control of rice root nematode by carbofuran in Orissa, India, 1983-84.^a

Treatment	Nematode population/ 200 cc soil				Population/ g root		Flowering tillers (no.)		Fresh root weight at harvest (G)		Yield/plot (kg)	
	Before transplanting		At harvest		1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984	1983	1984
	1983	1984	1983	1984								
T	134.6	119.4	250.2	315.2	7.20	6.20	3.48	4.80	25.30	18.44	2.2	2.7
T2	132.0	124.8	140.0	151.0	4.16	4.00	4.10	6.20	29.28	20.70	2.6	2.9
T3	134.4	109.6	69.0	90.0	2.66	3.20	4.56	6.60	34.64	26.70	3.0	3.3
T4	122.4	126.0	14.0	22.6	0.84	1.40	5.26	7.40	40.74	31.82	4.0	4.4
CD (0.05)	15.0	20.4	14.6	18.8	0.40	1.32	1.38	1.35	2.95	1.85	0.2	0.2

^aMean of 5 replications

Irrigation Water Management

Irrigation regime and rice yield

V.N. Khade, B.P. Patil, S.T. Thorat, and S.A. Khanvilkar, Konkan Agricultural University, Dapoli 415712 Maharashtra, India

We assessed the effect of irrigation level on rice yield (Ratna variety) during three dry seasons 1983-86. Soil was medium black, with pH 6.4, 0.87% organic C, and an infiltration rate of 1.0-1.4 cm/h. Seven treatments were replicated three times in a randomized block design.

One-month-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing and fertilized with 100-2241 kg NPK/ha. Irrigation treatments were scheduled immediately after transplanting. Water use efficiency was calculated on the basis of pooled means.

In all 3 yr, irrigation level significantly influenced yield (see table). Irrigation at 12 mm cumulative pan evaporation (CPE) with 60 mm depth produced significantly higher grain yield (5.5 t/ha) than with 36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 12 mm CPE with 120 mm

Rice yield as influenced by irrigation. Maharashtra, India, 1983-86 dry seasons.

Irrigation ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				Water use efficiency (kg/ha • mm)	Irrigation applications (no.)	Water applied (mm)
	1983-84	1984-85	1985-86	Mean			
As required to maintain saturation	5.5	6.6	4.3	4.8	1.7	84	2815
12 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	5.1	6.4	5.0	5.5	2.3	40	2400
24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	4.7	6.7	4.4	5.3	3.7	24	1440
36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth	3.4	6.0	4.0	4.5	4.6	16	960
12 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	4.2	5.1	3.6	4.3	0.9	40	4800
24 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	4.3	6.1	3.7	4.9	1.7	24	2880
36 mm CPE with 120 mm depth	3.8	6.9	3.9	4.9	2.5	16	1920
CD (0.05)	0.4	1.0	0.6	0.6			

^aCPE = Cumulative pan evaporation.

depth. It produced yield equal to 24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 24 and 36 mm CPE with 120 mm depth.

Water use efficiency was highest (4.6 kg/ha.mm) with irrigation at 36 mm CPE with 60 mm depth. The

quantity of water required was 960 mm from transplanting to maturity.

Irrigation at 12 mm CPE with 60 mm depth and 24 mm CPE with 60 mm depth resulted in equal yields, but 24 mm CPE saved 960 mm of water. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter and the IRRI Reporter are mailed free to qualified individuals and institutions engaged in rice production and training. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.